

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LINGUISTIC REPRESENTATION OF THE TERM "LIFE" IN L.N. ANDREEV'S PLAY "HUMAN LIFE"

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Abstract. This study explores the linguistic representation of the concept of "life" in L.N. Andreev's play Human Life, examining how language reflects the philosophical and cultural dimensions of existence. By analyzing the play through a conceptual framework, the research investigates how Andreev employs linguistic tools such as metaphors, epithets, and associations to construct a rich, multidimensional portrayal of life. Drawing on the theory of conceptual semantics, the study reveals that the concept of "life" is not only a central theme in the play but also serves as a vehicle for exploring broader existential questions about fate, value, and transience. The analysis highlights the role of the associative-semantic field in the play, where core and peripheral zones of meaning reflect both objective and subjective interpretations of life. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the significance of linguistic and cultural symbols in conveying Andreev's artistic worldview, where life is depicted as a fragile and transient phenomenon, shaped by fate yet deeply valued. This work contributes to the understanding of how linguistic representations in literature can reveal deeper cultural and philosophical insights, offering a comprehensive view of the human experience as reflected in language.

Keywords: linguistic representation, concept of life, conceptual semantics, metaphors, associative-semantic field, linguistic picture of the world, cultural symbols, existential themes, fate, transience, artistic worldview.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматривается языковая репрезентация концепта «жизнь» в пьесе Л.Н. Андреева «Жизнь человека», изучается, как язык отражает философские и культурные измерения бытия. Анализируя пьесу с помощью концептуальных рамок, авторы исследуют, как Андреев использует такие языковые средства, как метафоры, эпитеты и ассоциации, чтобы создать богатое, многомерное изображение жизни. Опираясь на теорию концептуальной семантики, исследование показывает, что понятие «жизнь» не только является центральной темой пьесы, но и служит средством для исследования более широких экзистенциальных вопросов о судьбе, ценности и преходящести. Анализ подчеркивает роль ассоциативно-семантического поля в пьесе, где ядро и периферийные смысловые зоны отражают как объективные, так и субъективные интерпретации жизни. Кроме того, в исследовании подчеркивается значение языковых и культурных символов в передаче художественного мироощущения Андреева, где жизнь изображается как хрупкое и преходящее явление, формируемое судьбой и в то же время глубоко ценное. Данная работа вносит вклад в понимание того, как языковые репрезентации в литературе могут раскрывать более глубокие культурные и философские идеи, предлагая всесторонний взгляд на человеческий опыт, отраженный в языке.

Ключевые слова: языковая репрезентация, концепт жизнь, концептуальная семантика, метафоры, ассоциативно-семантическое поле, языковая картина мира, культурные символы, экзистенциальные темы, судьба, быстротечность, художественное мировосприятие

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot L.N. pyesasidagi "hayot" tushunchasining lingvistik tasvirini o'rganadi. Andreevning "Inson hayoti" asari til borliqning falsafiy va madaniy o'lchovlarini qanday aks ettirishini o'rganadi. Asarni kontseptual asos orqali tahlil qilgan mualliflar, Andreevning hayotning boy, ko'p qirrali tasvirini yaratish uchun metafora, epithet va assotsiatsiya kabi lingvistik vositalardan qanday foydalanishini tekshiradi. Kontseptual semantika nazariyasiga asoslanib, tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, "hayot" tushunchasi nafaqat asarning markaziy mavzusi, balki taqdir, qadriyat va o'tkinchilik haqidagi kengroq ekzistensial savollarni o'rganish uchun vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Tahlil assosiativ-semantik maydonning assosiativ-semantik sohaning rolini ta'kidlaydi, bu erda asosiy va periferik semantik zonalar hayotning ob'ektiv va sub'ektiv talqinlarini aks ettiradi. Bundan tashqari, tadqiqotda Andreevning badiiy dunyoqarashini etkazishda lisoniy va madaniy timsollarning ahamiyati ta'kidlangan, bunda hayot mo'rt va o'tkinchi hodisa sifatida tasvirlangan, taqdir taqozosi bilan shakllangan va ayni paytda chuqur qadrlanadi. Ushbu ish adabiyotdagi lingvistik tasvirlar inson tajribasining tilda aks ettirilgan har tomonlama ko'rinishini taklif qilish orqali chuqur madaniy va falsafiy g'oyalarni qanday ochib berishi mumkinligini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: til tasviri, hayot tushunchasi, kontseptual semantika, metafora, assosiativ-semantik maydon, dunyoning lingvistik tasviri, madaniy timsollar, ekzistensial mavzular, taqdir, o'tkinchilik, badiiy dunyoqarash.

The integration of various private areas of scientific knowledge, associated with the popularisation of the opinion that it is effective and productive to study any phenomenon, as well as more complex, voluminous phenomena (e.g., human life, the process of social development, philosophical categories), only by relying on the achievements of various sciences (exact, natural, humanities), which together allow us to form the most complete ideas about them, brings to the forefront the relevant objects that have opportunities for a comprehensive understanding of them. Among them it is necessary to point out the 'concept', the content of which is identical to the word 'concept' (as pointed out, for example, by V.N. Surina [1]). The meaning of each concept is extremely generalised and is revealed in a whole bundle of smaller meanings denoted by words, series of words and expressions united by various semantic links (this is noted in their works by V.A. Pishchalnikova [2], E.I. Sheigal [3] and others).

Concepts are usually referred to, first of all, those concepts that are of primary importance for the linguistic picture of the world of native speakers, often similar in different languages, but in a new, special way in them are revealed due to their mental and ethno-cultural conditionality (which has been repeatedly emphasised by such scientists as L. O. Cherneiko [4], N. R. Surodina [5], G. V. Prikhodko [6], O. G. Pocheptsov [7], V. I. Karaptsov [7], V. I. Karaptsov [7]). O. Cherneiko [4], N.R. Surodina [5], G.V. Prikhodko [6], O.G. Pocheptsov [7], V.I. Karasik [8], S.G. Vorkachev [9], etc.). The spheres of functioning and fixation of concepts are: 1) language reflected in the dictionary; 2) oral/written speech; 3) language consciousness, etc., which explains the impressive potential of their multidimensional study. As E.I. Kuznetsova notes, 'the latest studies of the relationship between language and thinking allow us to consider concepts not only in philosophical, but also in linguistic, cultural and other aspects, a large number of their interpretations, classifications and research methods are proposed' E.V. Obraz-Tsova also points to the need for multidimensional scientific understanding of concepts and the application of an integrative approach to their study. 'The reason for such a versatile view of this phenomenon is the fact that the information contained in the concept is extremely multifaceted:

it provides information about the designated object from all sides, in all the variety of its manifestations and connections with other objects’, - explains E.I. Kuznetsova further

Conceptual studies in Russian linguistics have been very popular in recent decades because they allow us to study the semantic basis of language as a cognitive system, to identify the specificity of its reflection of the peculiarities of world perception and worldview of its speakers, which at the thinking level determine the national constants of thinking, and at the linguistic level form the linguistic picture of the world. According to A.R. Gabbasova's definition, the linguistic picture of the world is ‘reality reflected in the language, the linguistic membership of the world, information about the world transmitted by means of language units of different levels’ However, language units themselves are not fragments, materially expressed particles of the linguistic picture of the world: this status is acquired either by the most culturally significant elements, metaphorically complicated and reinterpreted (cultural symbols), or by elements involved in the expression of basic concepts - concepts (‘Love’, ‘Wisdom’, ‘Faith’, etc.), representing a certain conceptual area - a part of the linguistic picture of the world.

The main structural component of the linguistic picture of the world is a concept - ‘the content side of a verbal sign, behind which there is a concept related to the mental, spiritual or material sphere of human existence, fixed in the social experience of the people, having historical roots in their lives, socially and subjectively comprehended and - through the stage of such comprehension - correlated with other concepts related to it or, in many cases, opposed to it’ [13]. The content of a concept, as we have already emphasised above, can be marked by linguocultural specificity, but its primary importance in it, as well as the remoteness of its semantics from the basic meaning of the identifier turns it already into a cultural symbol, also undoubtedly important in the mastering of the linguistic picture of the world. Thus, the concept is the leading means and tool of cognition of the linguistic picture of the world, mainly in linguophilosophical and linguocultural aspects.

The results of observations of the artistic concept ‘Life’ in L.N. Andreev's play ‘The Life of Man’, it is possible to trace how the content of mental-cognitive structures, which are now the result of individual cognition and generalisation and have an image and value essence, is revealed in the artistic text through language. The concept ‘Life’, which is significant for L.N. Andreev's artistic worldview, has found a rather diverse linguistic expression in the text of the play ‘The Life of a Man’.

The linguistic means directly or indirectly (associatively) expressing the concept ‘life’ are united on the basis of semantic or associative links into an associative-semantic text field with a corresponding ‘name’. The core and near-core zones of the field, containing linguistic units, which are connected with each other by semantic similarity, reflect the objective content of the concept ‘Life’; the peripheral zone, which includes units based on the author's own associations, reflects the subjective content of the concept, as well as the main problem of the play ‘Human Life’ - the interpretation of life as an image and value essence, its subordination to the power of Fate, Rock and at the same time its finitude, transience. A rich palette of artistic techniques that increase the expressiveness of the narrative (repetitions, including anaphoric, epithets, metaphors, comparisons, etc.), which act as micro-concepts in relation to the hyper-concept ‘Life (human)’ in the author's artistic worldview, contributes to the fullest and most accurate disclosure of the main idea of the play and its central concept ‘Life’. All this together helps L.N. Andreev to emphasise the true value of human life and the necessity for each person to live it with dignity and pride. This determines the importance and necessity of conceptological research on artistic material in order to expand knowledge about the potential semantics of linguistic

units, which is realised only in a certain context, about the very artistic and artistic worldview of L.N. Andreev.

In conclusion, the concept of "life" in L.N. Andreev's play *Human Life* is portrayed through a linguistic field rich in both objective and subjective elements, underscoring the author's view of life as a fleeting yet valuable experience. By employing metaphors, literary devices, and associations, Andreev provides a multifaceted exploration of life, emphasizing its fragility, its relation to fate, and its importance as a cultural symbol. This linguistic representation serves not only as a vehicle for artistic expression but also as a reflection of the broader philosophical and cultural understandings of life.

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